

LIMNOLOGY AROUND THE WORLD: BRAZIL

The Culture Collection of Freshwater Microalgae from the Federal University of São Carlos (CCMA-UFSCar), Brazil

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Microalgae and cyanobacteria have great ecological and economical importance. They are the main primary producers in aquatic systems, and some may produce harmful blooms (e.g. Field *et al.*, 1998; Paerl *et al.*, 2001). Moreover, in the last decades, there has been a growing use of these microorganisms in various industrial sectors, e.g. food, pigments, pharmaceuticals, cosmetics (Borowitzka, 2013; Borowitzka *et al.*, 2016). In spite of this, so far just a small portion of microalgae and cyanobacterial diversity has been explored for biotechnological and commercial purposes (Harvey, 2000; Senhorinho *et al.*, 2015), and much of their diversity is still unknown (Guiry, 2012; De Vargas *et al.*, 2015).

Some studies on algal ecology and research for biotechnological and commercial uses demand isolated strains that are usually requested from (and/or deposited in) culture collections. Therefore, these collections are important centers of *ex situ* conservation of genetic resources, providing strains and services for both academic and non-academic purposes.

The culture Collection of Freshwater Microalgae from the Federal University of São Carlos (CCMA-UFSCar, Portuguese acronym for Coleção de Culturas de Microalgas de Água Doce da Universidade Federal de São Carlos) is located in the Phycology Laboratory,

Botany Department. The CCMA-UFSCar (World Data Centre for Microorganisms 835), formerly named UFSCarCC (http://ccinfo.wdcm.org/collection/by_id/835), was the first culture collection of freshwater microalgae founded in Brazil, in 1977, by Prof. Armando Augusto Henriques Vieira (Lourenço & Vieira, 2004). Currently, it is probably the largest and most diverse collection of the kind in Brazil, besides being among the largest microalgae collections in Latin America.

Throughout these 45 years, the collection has been expanded and maintained mainly by grants from research projects. Its curation and maintenance have been taken care of by non-exclusive staff from UFSCar, and voluntarily by post-docs and students from the Phycology Lab.

Since its foundation, the CCMA-UFSCar has been providing training in algal culture curation, as well as offering strains of microalgae and cyanobacteria for educational and research purposes to schools, institutions and companies across the country. Since 2017 this has been done through an institutional outreach project at UFSCar, and it has been possible to request restitution for maintenance costs. Unfortunately, due to the lack of dedicated staff for the culture collection and some constraints that derive from Brazilian laws, shipping strains abroad is difficult. In the last four years, only within Federal University of São Carlos, our collection provided strains for at least 29 projects (from post-doc to undergraduate research) funded by FAPESP (Fundação de Amparo à Pesquisa do Estado de São Paulo), CNPq (Conselho Nacional de Desenvolvimento Científico e Tecnológico) and CAPES (Coordenação de Aperfeiçoamento de Pessoal de Nível Superior).

All strains at CCMA-UFSCar are maintained as metabolically active cultures (Fig. 1), which demands time and effort; also, some replicates are cryopreserved (Tessarolli *et al.*, 2017). We have approximately 670 strains from Brazil and we also keep around 120 strains from other countries (Fig. 2). From these, about 170 are also kept in axenic cultures, which may be important for some biotechnological application, since interactions with bacteria and fungi can alter the production and degradation of compounds (e.g. Bruckner *et al.*, 2011; Stengel *et al.*, 2011). Most of the strains were isolated from reservoirs, small ponds, streams, springs, and bogs at São Paulo State, half of it during a research project BIOTA-FAPESP coordinated by Prof. Armando Vieira, but we have also isolated strains from other regions (Fig. 2). Since the focus of the Phycology lab projects has been green microalgae, most of the isolated algae are chlorophytes and some streptophytes, but we also cultivate cyanobacteria, cryptophyceans, xanthophyceans, chrysophyceans, and diatoms.

Fig. 1 The Culture Collection of Freshwater Microalgae at the Federal University of São Carlos (CCMA-UFSCar).

Most of the strains have been identified based on morphological features, which are usually insufficient for morphologically simple microalgae (Krienitz & Bock, 2012; Fawley & Fawley, 2020). This means that we have possibly underestimated the diversity of the collection. Recently, 150 strains of green microalgae were analyzed by morphological and molecular techniques, leading us to identify three new species and reposition one family within the Chlorophyceae (Garcia *et al.*, 2017; Garcia *et al.*, 2021). We also estimate that around 20% of the remaining strains within this dataset belong to at least six more new species/genera (including picoeukaryotes). Thus, we have much more to discover in the Culture Collection. This is also true for biotechnological applications. For example, in a screening for promising biodiesel producers, one strain from our culture collection produced 115% more fatty acids than soybean (Menezes *et al.*, 2013).

Fig. 2 Countries from where the strains maintained at the CCMA-UFSCar were isolated. Most of the strains were isolated from Brazil, mainly from São Paulo State.

Although the correct identification of strains is important for applications and commercial use (please, see references in Borowitzka, 2016), most of the identification has been done by PhD students and postdocs, which limits the number of strains used. In 2018 we received a grant from FINEP (Financiadora de Estudos e Projetos, Brazilian Federal Government) that specifically aimed to improve quality of the collection. This project allowed us to obtain molecular markers for 100 strains and to get infrastructure for cryopreservation and data curation. Increasing the number of cryopreserved strains is important for the quality of the Culture Collection, since it is more suitable for maintaining their long-term genetic stability, fundamental for basic and applied science. By 2023 we expect to make available at the [Phycology Lab page](#) data about the strains, such as identification, isolation site, culture medium used, and published papers. Despite funding for materials and equipment, we still lack personnel. Since most of our staff is composed of volunteer students, and the number of scholarships to postgraduate programs is getting scarce, this has been a growing constraint to keep the collection in good shape and to continue to offer services to the community.

Currently, besides the project funded by FINEP, another two wider research projects are helping to maintain the CCMA-UFSCar: 1) Bioprospection, characterization and optimization of Brazilian microalgae for CO₂ biofixation and production of commercially important biomolecules, funded by FAPESP and Coordinated by Prof. Ana Teresa Lombardi, and 2) Ecological species concept applied to the specific delimitation of asexual green microalgae, funded by CNPq and coordinated by Prof. Inessa Lacativa Bagatini.

In the future, we hope that Brazilian funding agencies and government realize the importance of keeping these important and unexplored genetic resources that are culture collections. Furthermore, understanding that culture collections (which includes the ability to provide strains) require a lot of work and dedicated personnel must be attained. The reality of collections being undervalued and not funded must come to an end.

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